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European forum and oBsErVatory for OPEN science in transport

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Executive summary

The present deliverable is part of the WP6 “Dissemination and Engagement”[1] under Task 6.3 Social media interfaces and research communities’ engagement. It summarizes the development, guidelines and implementation of the BE OPEN social media interfaces and research communities’ engagement.

The aim of the BE OPEN social media interfaces is to be used, in connection to the project website (D6.1) [2], for the wide dissemination of the project and the communication of its scopes and findings to the involved stakeholders, the research community and the public.

Throughout the project duration these tools interfaces will be updated constantly, following the progress of the project work, in order to reflect the status of the project and to actively involve all related parties to its activities.

The present deliverable is divided in 5 main chapters. The *Chapter 1* presents the social media channels chosen for the project, for which a communication strategy has been defined and presented in *Chapter 2*. The *Chapter 3* describes the methodology for posting scheduling, which is consequently applied to the regular postings and the specific campaign actions which are then described in *Chapter 4*. The *Chapter 5* describes the key performances indicators (KPIs) used for measuring the impact of the social media strategy.

Disclaimer: This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
H2020	Horizon 2020 EU Research and Innovation Programme
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
TOPOS	Transport Observatory/Forum for Promoting Open Science
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The aim of this document is twofold: to set the communication channels for social media and Zenodo and provide a social media strategy to engage a wide audience in the field of open science in transport.

Furthermore, BE OPEN will capitalize on the networking potential of each partner involved and multiply the outreach of the project’s dissemination and awareness raising activities. These specific communication and dissemination activities will run from month 6 to month 30.

1.1. Target groups and chosen social media channels

The target groups, as defined in the BE OPEN Grant Agreement and refined in the Dissemination Strategy [3] are:

- Users of open science in transport, namely: researchers/students, universities/research centres, transport networks, industry, policy makers and, general public.
- Producers and facilitators of open science: industry, researchers, universities/research centres, publishing portals and repositories, indexation companies.

Figure 1. Target groups

Based on the Target groups and the kind of project, a set of social media channels has been chosen in order to raise awareness and maximise exposure.

1.2. Twitter

Twitter® is an online news and social networking site. What makes Twitter different from most other social media sites is that it has a strong emphasis on real-time information — things that are happening right now. It is a great channel to spread project news but also to

interact and to connect with a wide audience and is surely an important channel in this kind of project due to the frequent use of twitter in the sector. Twitter offers direct communication via comments and retweets, which will create an environment for conversations. Another tool is the Twitter lists where content can be more specific and more precise in targeting the foreseen audience.

A dedicated Twitter account has been created by ECTRI ([@OpenScTransport](#)) in June 2019 and will be used for a big scale bidirectional communication, with all the users present on this social media, though converging to a more technical audience from transport researchers, transport related industry, policy makers, publishing houses and other open access stakeholders. This media will be crucial for Events, Conferences or Workshops to live broadcast the key discussions, messages and outcomes, as well as attracting new followers through real time information. By generating followers, a BE OPEN community will be developed, sharing the news in time and increasing interaction.

Figure 2. BE OPEN Twitter account screenshot

1.3. LinkedIn

As the largest professional networking site, LinkedIn® offers an excellent tool for connecting to the expert community working both in transport research and open science. BE OPEN has decided to create a LinkedIn group page aiming to create an expert community of BE OPEN partners and related stakeholders in order to enhance collaboration and engagement. It will serve as a first interface in the perspective of the Forum on Open Science in Transport to be created in the frame of the project.

The BE OPEN LinkedIn group (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12262083/>) has been launched in June 2019 constituting a place for dissemination of results, publications and promotion of events. All project partners are invited to join the group and to invite their relevant contacts to do so as well.

Figure 3. BE OPEN LinkedIn Group screenshot

Content will be managed by ECTRI and EURNEX. Partners are encouraged to:

- Provide input regarding news that should be promoted.
- Launch discussions and write their own contributions via their personal profiles.

BE OPEN LinkedIn members will also be able to exchange views and experiences on BE OPEN related topics while the stakeholders will be able to give their input in discussions around the main outcomes of the project.

1.4. Facebook

The consortium agreed not to create a project Facebook account and concentrate efforts on LinkedIn and Twitter, as they are considered a more professional driven platforms and thus providing a more relevant way to build a community and reach a stronger engagement.

1.5. Zenodo

Zenodo.org is a general-purpose open-access and open source repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefacts.

In this regard, BE OPEN will analyse Zenodo’s existing content in relation to transport and to clarify the need for further creating and maintaining a living transport research community on that platform, for linking BE OPEN’s outputs to other deposited research within Horizon 2020 grants and finally for understanding how this tool can be linked to the TOPOS / Observatory to be created as output of the project.

2. Social Media Strategy

The goal in using social media is to:

- Create Awareness on the project and its main results and start conversations.
- Engage with a large audience but also focus on key stakeholders.
- Complement traditional communications channels e.g. printed publications, events, press outreach and targeted mailings.
- Promote project events and engage with participants.
- Provide on-site coverage of key events.
- Maximise the return on investment by steering additional traffic to the BE OPEN website.
- Evaluate the impact of dissemination actions by monitoring mentions, followers and user’s engagement with BE OPEN pages and messages.

The overall goals can be translated into the following measurements and metrics (KPIs):

Table 1. Social media goals and metrics (KPIs)

Social media goals	Metric(s)
Awareness	Followers, shares, etc
Engagement	Comments, likes, @mentions, etc
Conversations	Website visits, email signups, subscriptions etc
Direct interactions	Live tweeting on events, on site coverage
Impact	Testimonials, ambassadors, etc
Evaluation	Tracking, monitoring

The strategy and guidelines for each selected social media are the following:

2.1. Twitter-strategy

- Create the BE OPEN account [@OpenScTransport](#) and hashtag(s), which will be used consistently throughout the overall project implementation. Hashtags (#) are used to reach specific target groups and identify key concepts. Two to five hashtags per tweet is recommended.
- Use recognized and institutional handles in the tweets to maximise visibility and be recognized as part of the H2020 community.
- Make it visual with the use of pictures, videos, data visualizations in view to spark interest.

- Share posts and tag other Twitter accounts (up to 10), to build a relationship with our audience and make them aware of content that might interest them, in the hope that they will retweet it.
- Encourage conversations (by posing questions, thanking others that mentioned the project etc.)
- Leverage any existing social media presence, using existent partner’s platforms, official institutions (EC and INEA) and other running projects, and get all these parties to communicate information about BE OPEN.
- Create a BE OPEN Twitter list/ or sign up for already existing relevant lists. These lists can serve as channels for receiving news and provide pools of people/organizations who can share your posts, by tagging them or message them directly.
- Display the disclaimer as follows: “BE OPEN Project receives funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation Programme. Any related tweets reflect only the views of the project consortium.”

Table 2. Twitter identified hashtags and profile/account handles

Hashtags	Profile handles (non-exhaustive list)
#BEOPENproject #OpenScience #OpenScienceTransport #transportresearch #H2020Transport #investeu	@EU_H2020 @EUSciComm @inea_eu @CORDIS_EU @(BE OPEN partners)

2.2. LinkedIn-strategy

- Define the rules for participation and provide orientation to all users; clear guidelines not only provide a level of comfort that enables members to confidently participate in discussion, they can also reduce the moderation load because they lead to fewer posts that fall out of the Group scope; this set of rules will be published on Group Rules tab and in a discussion so members can provide feedback.
- Keep a regular presence with relevant news about projects activities, but also with those activities where the feedbacks from the community is highly valued.
- Use recognized and institutional handles in the posts to maximize visibility and be recognized as part of the H2020 community.
- Use the relevant hashtag(s) consistently throughout the overall project implementation.
- Make it visual with the use of pictures, videos and data visualizations in order to spark interest.
- Leverage any existing social media presence, using existent partner’s platforms, official institutions (EC and INEA) and other running projects, and get all these parties to communicate information about BE OPEN.

- Display a disclaimer as follows “The BE OPEN project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation under Grant Agreement No 824323.”

Table 3. LinkedIn identified hashtags and profile/account handles

Hashtags	Profile handles (non-exhaustive list)
#BEOPENproject #OpenScience #OpenScienceTransport #transportresearch #H2020Transport #investeu	INEA - Innovation and Networks Executive Agency European Commission Partners profiles

2.3. Zenodo-strategy

- Actions will be conducted to explore the need for creating a living transport-community during the BE OPEN project duration on Zenodo platform and how to maintain it after the project end period, in relation particularly to the TOPOS, Observatory to be created.
- If deemed relevant, such Zenodo Transport Community will be created where BE OPEN will be able to share/upload-link, export and upload, accept/reject contributions during and after the project
- Target audience will be defined, and the upload link shared with them in view to assure an active community

3. Posting scheduling

The social media strategies will be monitored and scheduled via a shared google document. In this document the partners ECTRI and EURNEX. eV will coordinate all actions and posting of news etc.

The Google document will follow the following structure:

- What? (What will be posted, shared, retweeted etc)
- Where? (On which social media channel?)
- When? (On which date?)
- Why? (What’s the purpose? To engage? To inform? To start a conversation?)
- Who? (Who will do it? ECTRI or EURNEX eV? Other partner?)

Table 4. Shared google schedule (example)

What?	Where?	When?	Why?	Who?
Welcome to the #beopenproject Twitter account! Here you will find the project latest news, events & publications but also key info on #openscience and #transportresearch . We invite you to discover this new initiative and contribute to the discussion! #H2020Transport @inea_eu	Twitter	20.06.2019	to launch the twitter account	ECTRI

4. Types of posting and frequency

Following the drafted Dissemination Strategy [3] - as the project's guidance document for all dissemination, communication and exploitation activities – BE OPEN will implement a strategy of cross-channel dissemination, here specifically a cross-linking between the social media, the webpage posting and content and the Partners' own platforms. Within the social media interfaces this will be implemented through regular posting and campaign actions.

Regular posting will cover day-to-day activities and updates on BE OPEN, such as, publications, surveys, project meetings, presence in external conferences, but also relevant external news and events.

The campaigns differs from regular social media posting because of their increased focus, targeting and measurability. BE OPEN has identified 5 major project milestones, which will be covered with tailored campaign actions, such as: creation of appealing visuals, cross posting between BE OPEN and partners platforms, implementation of calls to action/ interaction and live tweeting.

1. Launch of website and social media (M6)
2. 1st project event (M10)
3. International Workshop (M22)
4. TOPOS launch (M26)
5. Final project event (M28)

Table 5. Posting frequency and Campaign actions for Twitter and LinkedIn

Type of posting	Posting frequency
Regular posting	5-10 posts/month
Campaigns	Number of posts to be defined according to targets/needs

A shared google document will be used to schedule the social media posts.

The potential Zenodo-community will be promoted and linked via social media accounts and through the social media accounts invitations to join the community.

5. Monitoring and KPI's

BE OPEN will make sure that the proper tracking tools are in place to be able to measure the impact on social media, e.g. KPI's. The available tools - google analytics, Twitter Analytics, and Zenodo statistics etc. – will be used to monitor:

- Frequency: Number of posts published
- Audience Growth: New followers
- Reach: Reach and impressions
- Engagement: Interactions, views, comments, shares
- Traffic Generation: Referrals or quality visits from social media channels

The assessment of the indicators for the regular posting will be periodically evaluated and provided to the Coordinator in each Periodic reporting. Those KPIs will be assessed and reviewed after the first year to adapt to the social media posts' development and impacts.

Table 6. Types of posting and related quantitative KPIs

Type of posting	Quantitative KPIs
Regular posting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 new Twitter follower/LinkedIn member per week on the 1st year of project • 1 retweet/shared post every 2 weeks on the 1st year of project • by the week that follow the event • 1 comment every 2 weeks on the 1st year of project
Campaigns	
1. Launch of website and social media (M6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100 Twitter followers/LinkedIn members by M12
2. 1st project event (M10)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 new Twitter followers/LinkedIn members by the week that follow the event • 10 retweet/shared post every 2 weeks by the week that follow the event • 1-5 comments by the week that follow the event
3. International Workshop (M22)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>(To be defined in due time)</i>
4. TOPOS launch (M26)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>(To be defined in due time)</i>
5. Final project event (M28)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>(To be defined in due time)</i>

6. References

- [1] BE OPEN Grant Agreement (824323 — H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020/H2020-MG-2018-SingleStage-INEA)
- [2] D6.1 Project logo and website (submitted M6)
- [3] D6.2 Dissemination Strategy (due to be submitted M18)